

Origin of Human Intelligence and Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract:

We all know how Artificial Intelligence begins but how Human Intelligence was created? Artificial Intelligence was first introduced by John McCarthy in 1956, but where does this idea Intelligence comes from? Human intelligence! Who introduced the intelligence of humans? Artificial Intelligence is the science and engineering of creating intelligent machines that require human level intelligence to perform task (McCarthy, 1956). But what is Human Intelligence? How Human Intelligence is so powerful? There is a test Turing Test which is built by sir Alan Turing to test the machine whether it behaves like human or not? But how is human intelligence tested? How human responded? After All, why is Artificial Intelligence compared with Human Intelligence? Because we all know that humans are only living being that have the power to think rationally, rationally make decisions (Turing, 1950).

Why is Human Intelligence compared with AI? Human Intelligence is created by The All-knowing Allah and Allah created his noble creature and honoured him. Allah is the one who introduced the intelligence of humans. There is a story in the holy Quran, where Allah describes how Allah created and introduced Human Intelligence. In Surah Baqarah, ayah 31, 32, and 33. These ayah details what intelligence is, how it is powerful that Allah commanded his angels to prostrate.

Human Intelligence which is blessed by Allah, Al-'Aleem (The All knowing) and Al-Hakeem (The All Wise). Human Intelligence is what Allah blessed to human as a gift. Allah created first human being Adam (A.S.) from clay and breathed a soul into him. He was given knowledge, which distinguished him from the angels, who were commanded to prostrate before him out of reverence. Allah taught Adam A.S. names, just like we equipped machines with data, all kind of data and done machine learning to build AI system. Similarly human also learned name which is taught by Allah. Human knowledge base which is engineered by Allah himself. Then Allah tested Adam (A.S.) in front of angles, Allah said to him "Inform them of their names", and he immediately responded within seconds (Qur'an 2:31–33; Russell & Norvig, 2021).

Thus, like human, who created their intelligent machine, that human proud to have their intelligence and making these intelligent machines. This intelligent is all given to or gifted to human from their Rab! This is Allah! Allah is everywhere and Allah proud himself to have his wonderful creation humans and loves him the most! All AI machines, automated systems, IOT devices which is created by Human Intelligence, this Intelligence is created by top level authority Allah!

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Human Intelligence (HI), Machine Learning (ML), knowledge Base (KB), Automated Systems (AS), Internet of Things (IOT).

Introduction:

This paper examines the origin of human intelligence and AI. intelligence is Powerful quality of human and it is Endowed to humans. the process involved in training human brains the knowledge is nothing different from how human train the AI

system and machine learn these models to perform their task (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

Allah SWT taught human the names of all things and describes in his book through his Ayat how human learn from the data feed (The Holy Qur'an, n.d., 2:31–33). The same strategies are applying to train AI machine. Machines are built by collecting datasets, training, testing, design

algorithm, using neural network machine learning, deep learning and through all these processes a machine build and based on given data. It draws inference by analysing the prompts given to machines.

Humans proud to build such intelligent system but he forgets that who gave him this intelligence. And all the strategies of building a same as it is already taught to human by Allah! humans are not first to build such powerful machines; Allah is the one who allow human the wonderful creation of him to build such powerful system (Russell & Norvig, 2021).

Problem Statement:

Human build a powerful artificial intelligence machine. Human intelligence evolves but humans also have to remember who originated and created humans. Allah lord of the skies and Earth, bestowed intelligence to humans and humans have to remind themselves where they belong to.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the origin and evolution of human intelligence
- To study the comparison of human intelligence and artificial intelligence both the strategies of creating intelligence are the same to an extent.
- To appreciate the beauty and purpose of one who originates and evolves intelligence

Methodology:

This study is based on the secondary data while the interpretation and thematic organization of the concept conducted by the researcher. Information was gathered from book, scholar's ideas. Ayat collected from holy Quran. Themes grouped and interpreted.

Data Collection & Analysis:

Allah describes the following ayat in the Quran.

Figure 1: (Surah Al-Baqarah 2:31 Al-Quran)

Translation:

He taught Adam the names of all things, then He presented them to the angels and said, "Tell Me the names of these, if what you say is true?" (Surah Al-Baqarah 2:31 Al-Quran)

Allah creates first human being first time 'Adam'. He taught Adam the names of all things, names of all things the first to the facts of all things, nouns, adjectives verbs etc. All things related to this world and what Allah taught from heaven. Human have some acquired knowledge, which human get by all his senses, from the environment. The senses of hearing seeing, touch, taste and smell. brain translate this input data to some logical inference. these are acquired knowledge. And this knowledge expands everyday new theories, inventions, technologies are exploring today just by what taught to human.

For example, in ancient time when there is no word for energy and someone watch How mountains collide and how fire burnt, this observation was enough for creating fire and then they Cook their food by rubbing stones that heats up and Spark, using this heat they warm themselves in cold and done their task. this is what the form of energy and development happens time to time and energy takes different form like electrical energy, chemical energy atomic and nuclear energy etc, and now human try to make nuclear energy which is eco-friendly. From rubbing the stones to developing energy through rays, which is invisible still human explorers from hardware to make things software. these all exploration and evaluation happen time to time from what human taught.

The angels thought that these humans will cause corruption on earth, they spill blood, murder each other on earth. And we declare your place and sanctify you. But then Allah said I know that what

you don't know. Allah taught and acknowledged Adam the names of all things, the things refer to which was present their, it includes children of Adam, he was taught everyone's name the personality and many other things. Then Allah represents all of them and said to Angels tell me names of all these if you are truthful. This refers that Angels really know about all of them then tell.

Figure 2: (Surah Al-Baqarah 2:32 Al-Quran)

Translation:

They replied, "Glory be to You! We have no knowledge except what You have taught us. You are truly the All-Knowing, All-Wise." (Surah Al-Baqarah 2:32 Al-Quran)

The angels declare perfection of Allah. They do tasbeeh of Allah. Which means:

سبح is to swim

السباحة to swim without dipping under second

سبجًا constant activity with no downtime

From this the abstract idea of not being thought down in any way became the meaning of تسبيح (tasbih).

The two main idea of tasbeeh:

1. What doesn't befit His Majesty's perfection. That is not say anything that brings down his perfection and not say something that doesn't appropriate for him.
2. The absolute and flawless nature of his lordship that he doesn't create anything purposeless.

The angels are creation of God who are created for specific purpose. Angels doesn't know anything except what they have been taught. Angels have their specific knowledge that related to their field. They know only about their task. Some of them appointed over wind, some assigned for mountains, some assigned to rain and some only created to make tasbeeh of Allah.

angels are civil servants of Allah. they do only what Allah commanded to do for. that's why angels have a specification for their field. But human knowledge explores. It expands by version to version. From one thing to other new thing. It advances time to time. Adam taught potentially.

The Angels declares Allah's Perfection and acknowledge that Allah is all knowing and all wise.

Al-Aleem the all-knowing. The Angels did not know what kind of knowledge does human provided but they except that their assumption about humans might not true and Allah knows everything. The past that how Adam was created, how brain and all neural networks are designed and how they programmed to process all data through in. Allah knows the future. Angles thought that human will cause harm, do bad deeds. They will not see Allah and so not remember him. not thankful to Allah and worship another God with him. But Allah said I know what you don't know Allah knows, the Hidden that angels can't see, the open, the Unseen, the front and the behind. Allah knows everything.

Al-Hakeem the all wise. He has perfect wisdom. he has unlimited knowledge and true judgment. everything he does is based in Infinite Wisdom. Allah's plan is perfect. the plan of creating humans and taught knowledge, train how to process and how did respond is all from his perfect wisdom.

Consider the brain how it thinks, how it functions, how it is stores and Analysis information. how it distinguishes and processes the information in 11 million bits every second and it does this constantly. This is the brain that carries knowledge and wisdom.

Consider the eyes, ears, hurt, lungs, stomach, liver, kidneys, intestine, bladder, bones, blood vessels all work in harmony. It obviously must have had a wise creator. the wisdom and thought put inside the body and put into everything inside the universe could have only come from the wisest most perfect Creator and that is Allah Al Hakeem.

قَالَ يَتَدَمُّ أُنْيَهُمْ بِأَسْمَائِهِمْ فَلَمَّا أَنْبَأَهُمْ بِأَسْمَائِهِمْ قَالَ أَلَمْ أَقُلْ لَكُمْ إِنِّي أَعْلَمُ غَيْبَ
السَّمَوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ وَأَعْلَمُ مَا تُبْدُونَ وَمَا كُنْتُمْ تَكْتُمُونَ ﴿٣٣﴾

Figure 3: (Surah Al-Baqarah 2:33 Al-Quran)

Translation:

Allah said, “O Adam! Inform them of their names.” Then when Adam did, Allah said, “Did I not tell you that I know the secrets of the heavens and the earth, and I know what you reveal and what you conceal?”

(Surah Al-Baqarah 2:33 Al-Quran)

By teaching all names to Adam Allah pointing him what around and said tell me names of these things and Adam responded frequently. The intelligence that he provided is from wisdom of Allah. He described the name by seeing the things and make difference by their colours. Some of them were sound that he listens and reply. Some were fragrance that he smells. This is testing of Adam that Allah done intelligence of Adam to angles. How Allah created and design the nervous system connected to all body parts nose, eyes, ears, skin sensors to brain and this brain processes all data to information and it becomes knowledge then he answered. This is Allah Al Hakeem and Al Hakeem. Therefore, angle prostate to Adam, not to worship him but Allah commanded to do so, to honour him. What a perfect Creator is!

One argument is that if creation is imperfect how can it point to perfect creator? Because humans are not perfect, they are imperfect. the entire universe changes every second!

As a beautiful painting reflects the creativity of artist, Well construct building reflects the Perfection of engineer, the perfection can be seen in the things which are not changing, that's why they perfect. If everything changes in the universe how it can be perfect, as every creation speaks for its creator. How can be the creator is perfect if his creation is imperfect!

This idea can be defined by:

1. The argument of beauty
2. The argument of purpose

If there is a beautiful painting it automatically gets attention, it looks beautiful. but two to three days the same painting loses its attraction. After some days it becomes normal, the taste gets reduced. It happens for everything which looks at first glance beautiful but after a few days or week it becomes no one as it only feels good but not like first day!

And second the perfection in purpose. Humans are imperfect the universe is imperfect. everything is in motion Sun, Moon, earth etc. But behind it is purpose.

For example, the motion of Earth and Moon and Sun around themselves. because of this motion there is morning and night happens on Earth so that work and sleep have a specific time. the purpose behind is perfect.

All this is from wisdom of Allah, that everything looks beautiful one who see and it should also have a specific purpose. That's what Allah said didn't I tell you that indeed I know the Unseen the skies and Earth. Allah reminds Adam and the angels that He knows the unseen.

Thus, human intelligence was created the process exactly same as an artificial intelligence.

For building an AI models the first is collecting data sets, clean the data for required use, but for Allah he is All Knowing, Allah's knowledge encompasses over everything. He blessed you the purpose. He from his wisdom provide knowledge to Human. Human distinguishes Thing by labelling some names to specific object, concepts, emotions then he better understand the concept behind it. In machine learning where data taught to machine to learn from data, find patterns and make decisions and prediction. The learning involves in machine learning are supervised learning, unsupervised and the enforcement learning. In supervised learning, the system knows the input and output from data and

data preprocessing and feature engineering involves to train machine. then the models are selected like linear regression, decision making tree, support Vector machine etc. depending upon the purpose of machine.

From the first Ayah it seems exact same. Allah taught Adam the names, can you play some music the date of everything and then he presents to angels and ask Angel, tell me about these things and adds if you are truthful. From this additional phrase Adam learned. He watches angels and analyses how they respond and he recognized the pattern by the phrase whether I should respond with truth or tellie. Data already feed to him. He had to make the decision to respond if next time Allah ask to him how he should respond. Whether he know about or not.

There is another term deep learning; a powerful process to train artificial neural networks with multiple hidden layers to automatically learn complex patterns and hierarchical representation from vast amount of data. this computational model inspired by human brain. And this human brain was designed and trained by Allah, the one to all Authority belongs.

This design done in a way that it automatically detect and translate data in any language. human nervous system, complex biological network is composed of billions of specialized nerve cells, or neurons, which use electrochemical signals to transmit information throughout the entire body. Like in machines the on or off signals are used to transmit information throughout the system.

Allah test Adam by asking him to define and he respond by analyse and think about those objects which is just like natural language processing NLP. The AI introduced by the question "Can machine think?" and thus human intelligence evolve!

Results & Discussion:

Allah allow this to happen. He made by filling the universe with all things to allow human to think and evolve so that they can remember Allah.

human see the aayat, the signs of Allah which is all around him. The skies, Sun, Earth, Moon, Mountains, trees, ocean Cloud, rain and many things so that humans can analyse and think about them. So that they remember Allah!

Conclusion:

The artificial intelligence is designed by human intelligence and this is at the top created by Allah. Artificial intelligence is limited but human intelligence is wide. Then what about the one who entirely created the universe. Allah knows the scene and unseen, what human can't see. humans should rely upon Allah. The truth is what Allah said.

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